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PRZEKSZTAŁCENIE ZARZĄDZANIA W WARUNKACH GLOBALNYCH WYZWAŃ

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Streszczenie. Artykuł uzasadnia konieczność przekształcenia administracji publicznej w kontekście globalnych wyzwań. Szybkość nowoczesnych procesów społeczno-gospodarczych, ekologicznych i informacyjnych wzrasta w zależności od prędkości sieci Internet. Zarządzanie w tych warunkach powinno być odpowiednie, zapewnione przez zapobiegawcze zarządzanie. Zarządzanie jest uważane za proces, którego wydajność jest określana przez odpowiednią sieć. Podczas pisania artykułu wykorzystano metody analityczne, procesowe i sieciowe. Treść metody prewencyjnej charakteryzuje się zdefiniowaniem dziesięciu etapów, które zapewniają pewność terminologiczną, analityczną charakterystykę obecnego stanu, konkretny cel i przewidywane, pożądane i możliwe wyniki, określenie uprawnień i odpowiedzialności podmiotów, inwentaryzację i obliczenie niezbędnych zasobów, charakterystykę sił napędowych, opracowanie strategii i taktyki osiągnięcia celów, stworzenie systemu gwarancji osiągnięcia celów, opracowanie systemu pomiaru i oceny skuteczności procesu osiągania wyznaczonych celów. Dane podejście pozwala przewidzieć przyszłe problemy i wczesne opracowanie mechanizmów ich eliminacji. Problemy są łatwiejsze do przewidzenia niż do wyeliminowania.

Słowa kluczowe: szybkość procesów, adekwatność zarządzania, prewencyjność, pewność, integralność, bliskość, kompletność, cykl, ocena, wydajność.

TRANSFORMATION OF MANAGEMENT IN THE CONDITIONS OF GLOBAL CHALLENGES

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Abstract. The article substantiates the necessity of transforming public administration in the context of global challenges. The speed of modern socio-economic, environmental, and information processes is increasing according to the speed of the Internet. Management under these conditions should be adequate, provided by preventive management. Management is considered as a process, the efficiency of which is determined by the corresponding network. When writing the article, analytical, process, networking methods were used. The content of the preventive method is characterized the definiteness of the ten stages that provide terminological certainty, the analytical characteristic of the current state, the specified goal and the predicted desired and possible results, the determination of the powers and responsibilities of the subjects, inventory and calculation of the necessary resources, the characteristics of the forces, the development of strategy and tactics of achieving the goals, the formation of the system guarantees of achievement of goals, development of a system of measurement and evaluation of the effectiveness of the process of achieving the goals set. This approach provides prediction of

future problems and early development of mechanisms for their elimination. Problems are easier to predict than to eliminate.

Key words: speed of processes, management adequacy, preventive, certainty, integrity, closeness, completeness, cycle, evaluation, efficiency.

ТРАНСФОРМАЦІЯ УПРАВЛІННЯ В УМОВАХ ГЛОБАЛЬНИХ ВИКЛИКІВ

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Анотація. У статті обґрунтовується необхідність трансформації державного управління в умовах глобальних викликів. Швидкість сучасних соціально-економічних, екологічних, інформаційних процесів зростає відповідно швидкості мережі Інтернет. Управління в цих умовах має бути адекватним, що забезпечується превентивним управлінням. Управління розглядається як процес, ефективність функціонування якого визначається відповідною мережею. При написанні статті застосовувалися аналітичний, процесний, мережевий методи. Зміст превентивного методу характеризується визначеністю десяти етапів, які забезпечують термінологічну визначеність, аналітичну характеристику сучасного стану, конкретизовану мету та прогнозовані бажані й можливі результати, визначеність повноважень і відповідальності суб'єктів, інвентаризацію та розрахунок необхідних ресурсів, характеристики рушійних сил, розробки стратегії й тактики досягнення цілей, формування системи гарантій досягнення цілей, розробки системи виміру та оцінки ефективності процесу досягнення поставлених цілей. Цей підхід забезпечує прогнозування майбутніх проблем та завчасної розробки механізмів їх усунення. Проблеми легше передбачити, ніж ліквідувати.

Ключові слова: швидкість процесів, адекватність управління, превентивність, визначеність, цілісність, замкненість, завершеність, цикл, оцінка, ефективність.

Introduction. At the beginning of the XXI century. humanity is undergoing globalization shifts. Transforms spheres that globally affect national states, societies, migration processes, employment of people, labor movement, etc. It is about the rapid development of the Internet, which is accompanied by the development of artificial intelligence, robotics, technology, technology, which led to the formation of the foundations of digital civilization, the transformation of the world economy, the emergence of new electronic currencies (crypto-currency) transformed world trade. Transformation is carried out at the speed of light: the rate of transformation is measured by the change in the speed of world money, which today is equal to the speed of the Internet. The result of the global influence of new spheres of the world economy is the formation of new forms of social organization "megassociety", and "the state loses the status of a single subject of integration and representation of the interests of large communities. The locus of management activity is dramatically expanding, shifting the emphasis from national to supranational and subnational levels. Globalization shifts led to a structural transformation of power systems and mechanisms, and revealed the pathology of the traditional administrative-bureaucratic concept of public administration "(Radziyevsky, 2006).

M. Castells, D. Kettle, O. Neclesa, G. Peters, and others made significant contributions to the systematization of new phenomena of a global scale. M. Castells

considers "the formation of international business and cultural networks and the development of information technology - as a phenomenon that is inextricably interconnected. All spheres of life, starting with the geopolitics of the great national powers and ending with the daily activities of people, are changing in the information space and global networks "(Castells, 2000, p. 5-7).

D. Kettle believes that in the 1980s the "global reform movement in the sphere of public administration" began. Firstly, it has captured many countries from Mongolia to the United States, and secondly, the reforms that are envisaged include broad-based goals: governments in the course of reforms define the role of the state and its relations with citizens in a new way (*Ketl, 2004*). O. Neclesa notes that "the change of current management codes is one of the most important aspects of change. New organizational schemes and technology sometimes simply undermine former institutions, changing the usual form of government. The tendency of marginalization of the corps of "legal power", national public policy, its alienation from the solution of a number of key issues, the substitution of social regulation by an alternative system, and the power of informal, transnational, geo-economic "(Economics of knowledge: the challenges of globalization and Ukraine, p. 230) begins to be seen. G. Peters emphasizes the fact that the global market, supranational authorities and institutions, local governments, and branch network structures (public and private) are struggling to be the driving force of society (*Peters, 2004*).

The development of globalization processes is not linear. Integration trends of globalization are accompanied by the development of regional structures. "National governments are in the grip between global forces and local needs. Today, the global market, supranational institutions, local authorities, and large public and private network structures compete for the right to play the role of the core power of social development management (*Radziyevsky, 2006*). Under these conditions, it is important to develop and develop instruments that national governments and local self-government bodies must meet with the needs of citizens in the formation of digital civilization, which can be ensured through the transition of the management system at the state and local levels to preventive principles.

The purpose of the article is to reveal the content of the management transformation in the context of global challenges, based on preventive methods of a closed, completed type.

Main part

Implementation of this goal requires the following tasks: to disclose the content of the preventive method; formalize the algorithm of the preventive management method.

In the process of writing the article applied methods: analytical, process, network. The implementation of the powers of local governments (local government) is considered as a closed, completed cycle, which is implemented on the basis of cycles: "citizen-state", "people-state", "cause-consequence", "beginning-end", "freedom-responsibility", "Justice - efficiency", "justice - force", "goal - results", "contradictions - harmony", "chaos - order", "unit (linear) - network"; criteria for evaluation of the closed cycle: social, economic, ecological, demographic, political, legal, informational, spiritual, moral, territorial, national, technological, etc. Each criterion has its own indicators, each indicator has its own measure (maximum, minimum, standard, fact).

Practical significance - Local governments receive incentive mechanisms for local communities, local authorities to improve local production; central authorities

receive methodological tools for preventive management, in particular, preventive assessment of the effectiveness of the ratio of state power and local self-government.

Results. The closed cycle of public administration is a causal and interdependent category that denotes a system of methodological foundations that, on the basis of appropriate mechanisms, should ensure the functioning of the primary network of society, realize the right of the people to be the bearers of sovereignty, the only source of power, and ultimately - to provide for themselves decent living conditions. Assessment of the degree of isolation - the standard of living of citizens is carried out according to social, economic, environmental, demographic, political, legal, informational, spiritual, moral, territorial, national, technological and other criteria. Each criterion has a set of indicators, each index has its own measure (maximum, minimum, standard, fact, absolute, relative).

In theory, a closed loop on which processes are carried out in different systems has the following characteristics. Closed Loop MRP (MRP) is a system built around Material Requirement Planning (MRP), which includes additional planning functions, such as production planning (aggregate planning), development of a main scheduling plan production planning (master production scheduling) and capacity requirements planning (planning). After the planning phase has been completed and plans have been adopted as realistic and achievable, plans are started, including production management functions, as measured I input-output (capacity) measurement, input-output (capacity) measurement, formation of detailed schedules and dispatching, as well as reporting on the expected lag from schedules from the factory and from suppliers, the formation of delivery schedules, etc. The term "closed cycle" "Means that these elements are not just included in the general system, but there is also a feedback from the execution functions, so that planning is always correct (Wikipedia. Closed MRP cycle).

Closure of a cycle is a process of organized actions of business entities aimed at ensuring the needs of citizens through causal transformations and displacement in time and space of software, material and intangible resources, etc.

The closure of the cycle in the economy serves as a collective consumption of goods as services. For example, public transport (metro, railways, bridges, tunnels, highways) guarantee the needs of citizens in transport.

Any action has the beginning and the end, which is one or another cycle. It is completed and not completed. The degree of completeness, closure of the cycle is established by a system for evaluating the effectiveness of local governments (local government). Completed is the cycle in which the goal is achieved, and the source components - more than the amount of incoming. Incomplete is a cycle in which the goal is not achieved. "Completed" and "not completed" cycles are methodological constants that should be taken into account when realizing the rights and freedoms of a citizen.

The terms "seclusion", "completeness" characterizes the existence of a causal relationship between the purpose of government and its results in time and space. They consider the functioning of the national economy (territorial community) as an appropriate cause-and-effect network, which should ensure the realization of the interests of the people (the local population) through the bodies of state administration (local self-government) that guarantee the provision of high-quality education services to the citizen, the population (community), culture, medicine, social protection, housing and communal services, ensuring the protection of public order and other vital areas, and which are endowed with sufficient and financial, infrastructure, personnel and other

resources. Each closed loop has a start, extension, and end, resulting in the loop closure of the completed form (Rule of the completed loop. Discussion on LiveInternet ...)

Formation of the bases of state, municipal management on the basis of a closed and completed cycle is a methodological basis, which should provide this process with high efficiency and efficiency. The degree of completeness of a cycle depends on the quality of methodological and methodological support, in particular, the conformity (accuracy) of terms, definitions, principles, methods, mechanisms of content and forms of community self-governance; completeness of the process of self-management by them; the same understanding of the cycle of self-governance by its actors involved in this process.

The closure of the cycle of state, municipal management is realized on the basis of the functioning of many cycles, in particular, such as: citizen - state, people - state, reason - consequence, beginning - end, freedom - responsibility, justice - efficiency ", " justice - force ", " goal - results ", " contradictions - harmony ", " chaos - order ", " unit (linear) - network ", etc. The development of managerial decisions of the Public Administration (local government), which should be based on the above mentioned cycles, should establish the truth in these ratios, that is, whether the goal set in the state (local) plans is achieved. If any of these and not named cycles will be established not optimally, citizens will not be able to provide a decent living conditions, the goal will not be achieved. The cycle will not be complete, not optimal.

Leading in the named system of cycles are cycles "cause - consequence", "meta - results". In the ratio of "cause - consequence", each side of the cycle must stand in its place. If the reason and the effect of changing places, the "meta-results" ratio radically changes, because the results will be directly opposite to the purpose.

In recent years, as a result of the reform of governance in Ukraine, local communities must take part in the process of ensuring living conditions. In the context of Article 5 of the Constitution of Ukraine, "The people are the bearers of sovereignty and the only source of power" (Constitution of Ukraine, 1996, p. 5), everything is logical. But at the same time, in order to implement this assertion, local communities need to be provided with adequate tools and resources in line with new authority.

As an integral system, a closed loop represents ten consecutive and functional steps that should be the basis of managerial decision on a preventive basis.

The first stage. Theoretical and methodological principles of managerial decision.

The second stage. Analysis of the state of development, adoption and implementation of managerial decisions.

The third stage. Formation of the purpose of managerial decision.

Fourth stage. Forecast of desired and possible results.

The fifth stage. Subjects of development, acceptance and realization of managerial decisions.

The sixth stage. Analysis of the status of resources, the potential for implementation of management decisions.

Seventh stage. Research of driving forces of development, acceptance and realization of managerial decisions.

Eighth stage. Development of strategy and tactics for the implementation of managerial decisions.

Ninth stage. Formation of a system of guarantees of implementation of strategy and tactics of managerial decisions.

Tenth stage. Formation of a system for evaluating the process of developing, adopting and implementing managerial decisions.

The development of these stages should take into account the challenges of the XXI century: the speed of the processes of transformation of the world economy; formation of digital civilization; formation of the digital total equivalent; the birth of artificial intelligence; information and network revolution; environmental challenges, global warming, environmental pollution; a constant increase in the cost of military means to destroy all living things on our planet; absence of guaranteed rules of international relations; migration processes; persistent military conflicts between countries, etc.

At the **first stage**, theoretical and methodological principles of managerial decisions are considered. The object and subject of public administration, methods, principles, mechanisms, tools and others are determined. Specifies the definitions, categories, methods, principles, etc., which should be unambiguous for the understanding of all participants in the socio-economic, political, etc. processes. These definitions should be made and consistent with the content of social processes. The object of public administration must be civil society, people. The subject is the standard of living of citizens.

The new algorithm for the development of managerial decisions involves identifying the starting point of the process from which any steps are taken, measures to match the object and subject of public administration. Such a point is the establishment of the principles of relations between actors on which all methods, mechanisms, definitions, terms, categories, instruments, etc. should be based.

The relations of the subjects of state and local government are based on the binary principles of freedom and responsibility, efficiency and justice.

We call these principles binary because they act only together in a certain ratio, which must be constructed to the appropriate extent and characterizes the level of civilization development of the state's economy. The guiding principle that determines their integrative interaction is the principle of freedom, which means the free choice of each subject of economic activity, equal access to business resources, fair protection of private property, etc. Activities of subjects of social development can not be arbitrarily limited either by the state or from the market.

In addition, the functioning of one principle at the expense of another is impossible without reducing the overall effect of their interaction. Compliance with the principle of freedom as the basic principle of a liberal economy must be ensured for entrepreneurs - an independent choice of areas of production activity; free access to financial, labor, natural resources; the need to protect their private property, in effective social activities, etc. ; citizens - free access to investment goods, end-consumer goods, free access through appropriate infrastructure to public administration; the state - satisfaction of the requirements for filling the budget for the implementation of investment functions, the organization of infrastructure for the implementation of its functions by civil society, etc.

The principle of freedom is realized through the binary principle - the principle of responsibility of subjects of management on the vertical: the state - the collective - the person and horizontally: the collective - the collective. The viability of the economic system and the efficiency of social production depend on the level of responsibility of the subjects. It should be noted that the decisive advantage of a market economy system

is the direct inclusion of each entity of state ownership in the liability relationship, the feature of which is the impossibility (in the presence of competition) of its absolute and concentration on one of the subjects of management (for example, the state or one of the subjects of the market) or self-removal from it leads to a command-administrative economy and the actual removal of other entities from ensuring the socio-economic efficiency of production. Self-exclusion from liability of individual economic entities leads, for example, to further shadowing of the economy observed in Ukraine, which by eliminating resources from official circulation reduces the potential of social development.

The main problem is the removal of uncertainties of the ratio of these principles to the vertical, horizontal and their optimization depends on time, place, measure, subjects (individuals, collective, civil society, state).

To eliminate the uncertainty of the correlation of these principles SB Crimean believed that "the standard of values characterizes scientific rationality as an alternative to dilettantism" (Crimean, 2003, p. 99). In modern view, the measure has not only quantitative-qualitative but also value aspects, acts not only as a unity of quality and quantity, but as a standard of any activity, the basis of harmony and expediency in modeling a person and his world.

For modern Ukraine finding optimum use of freedom, responsibility, justice, efficiency - the issue of ensuring the independence of the state. Indeed, it is necessary to adequately assess the time that Ukraine is living today; a place occupied geographically by Ukraine in the world economic space; the extent of these principles, when the domination of one of them leads to a fundamental change in the state system. For example, the use of unrestricted state laws of freedom leads to chaos in the state, and the use of unlimited liability, as shown by historical practice, leads to dictatorship.

The main problem when finding the optimum is to identify high-profile professionals. In this context, the transition from public administration to public administration involves changing not only the name but also the subject's changes. Civil society is replacing the state - the main trend of the modern world. The formation of civil society as the main subject brings powerful driving forces into economic development. In those countries where this does not happen, and only the name "state administration" changes to "public administration", the revolution is constantly being carried out. Power goes from one to the other, but nothing completely changes.

The second stage is an analysis of the state of development, adoption and implementation of management decisions. First of all, it is necessary to provide an objective assessment of the object and subject of managerial decisions - the state of economic development, determine where the country is, to indicate the world trends in the development of the economy, the state of the environment, social sphere, demography, technological and technological state, informatization and other and take this into account in new managerial decisions. For example, radical transformations are carried out in the economic sphere. The labor theory of value, as the basis for the formation of the price of goods, is replaced by the digital value of the goods, where the direct dependence of the price of the goods on the labor input disappears. This leads to the formation of a new total equivalent, which was gold and paper money, formed a digital cryptography, digital economy. The cardinal changes become the market of goods, which becomes the whole world. The work force moves freely around the world. In addition, robotics, which reduces jobs, is actively developing; In recent years, there is a large migration of active labor force. As a result, the economic boundaries of the state

disappear, and, therefore, in the future, the state will be transformed with the change of geographical boundaries.

The Internet is the most significant development, informatization of production, formation of world production networks, materials with new properties appear, new sources of energy are developing. Humanity is on the verge of a revolution in the energy sector. Oil and gas as energy carriers will be replaced by the latest sources.

The third stage involves the formation of the goal of state and local government. The most important thing in this context is the certainty of purpose. The question is always urgent: What society, which state we are building? At the state level, this concerns, first of all, the planning of measures to strengthen the state and the development of civil society as a subject, state and public administration. The state should, first of all, be interested in the development of public institutions, infrastructure, which should ensure the implementation of the functions of the subject of public administration. For this purpose, a network of citizens' education for their participation in public administration should be developed. Without a developed civil society, stable development of the state is impossible without forceful methods. And this leads to periodic revolutionary speeches of citizens who are not satisfied with state power.

At the fourth stage, the forecast of the desired and possible results of the implementation of public administration is being carried out. At this stage, positive and negative results of management decisions are projected. This is necessary in order to predict possible problems even before they arise, because after the problems arise, it is difficult to eliminate them, and sometimes it is impossible. Preventive measures should be developed not only to eliminate problems, but, above all, to predict them. This is the essence of the new procedure for the development, adoption and implementation of public decisions. This requires a detailed analysis of the past period of development of one or another sphere, which may contain problems that are only "waiting" for their launch. And this requires an analysis of the past 50 years or more. For example, social development scenarios should be foreseen when one of the actors - a state or a civil society - wants to usurp power.

At the fifth stage, the subjects are analyzed, which should participate in the development, adoption and implementation of management decisions. This is especially true for the participation of civil society institutions. So, in order for society's reforms to be perceived and implemented in the process of their preparation, civil society institutions should participate. Without this, all reforms will be on paper, but, as Ukrainian practice has shown, with negative consequences for people.

At the sixth stage, an analysis of the status of resources, the potential for the implementation of management decisions. First of all, at this stage, it is necessary to define the terms "potential", "resources". It is a matter of the fact that at each stage, the terms used in the planning of management decisions at each stage should be specified. For example, in Ukraine, terms that are not relevant to the content are often used. Yes, they argue that Ukraine has great potential, but there are no real results. Potential is what is actually used, and not something that can be used in the future. In this case, it is only the availability of resources, the realization of which requires the corresponding conditions that need to be created.

When developing management decisions, the amount of those resources, as it is, should be determined, those resources are determined that are necessary to achieve the goals, names and volumes of resources that are not available to achieve the goals. This

approach removes uncertainty in the development of managerial decisions, makes them real, and not virtual.

At the seventh stage, the driving forces of developing, adopting and implementing managerial decisions are explored. At the theoretical level, the driving forces are dialectical contradictions. This means that the development of the economy, society in this case occurs through revolution, insurrection, radical change of power, a new level.

At this stage, state bodies with the respective powers, functions, mechanisms and instruments must specify the problems of cooperation between public authorities and civil society institutions, which are today inhibiting and destabilizing social development in Ukraine.

Social development requires new driving forces, which are based not on contradictions, but on harmony, harmonization, and preventive. The point is that the main driving force of social development is the harmony of relations between government and civil society. The most valuable resource, which lies in one of the main conditions of the economic potential of the state, is the trust of civil society to power. Without this confidence, the real driving force is controversy, but through the revolution. True, during the revolution, huge resources are spent without benefits to meet the needs of citizens.

At the eighth stage, the development of strategy and tactics for the implementation of management decisions. After the uncertainty has been removed at the previous stages of development of management decisions by finding adequate terms and categories, an analysis of the situation in Ukraine and the world has been made, the goal for the authorities and civil society has been specified, the desired and possible results of the implementation of management decisions have been determined, an analysis of available and required resources has been made. and capacity, specified powers and responsibilities of actors in the process of developing, adopting and implementing management decisions, provided the scientific characteristic of p shiynyh forces specified existing and potential problems, training strategies and tactics development, adoption and implementation of management decisions. An analysis of the practice of transformation of economic development shows that concepts, strategies, programs are chaotically developed, minor problems are considered, but the strategies of economic development, civil society, state and public institutions are being developed chaotically, without observing the corresponding procedures, sequences and rules. The first steps in implementing such strategies, programs show that many issues were not explored, omitted, ignored, etc. The leading direction in developing the strategy of public decisions is the formation of mutual counterbalances between the state and civil society, which ensure the harmonious development of the economy, personality, and infrastructure of civil society. The main task of the tactics of public decisions is to develop institutional support for the harmonious influence of public authorities on civil society and institutional provision of the influence of civil society on state authorities. The legislative, executive, judicial branches of power and civil society influence the economic, political and other development of the main subjects of the economic process.

The lack of harmony of relations between the subjects of state and local government leads to chaos in society or to dictatorship.

At the ninth stage, a system of guarantees for the implementation of strategy and tactics of management decisions is implemented. All previous steps in this section

should be holistic, interconnected, closed, complete content and form. In the system of guarantees, the leading link is the semantic guarantees, the essence of which is that, on the one hand, all public decisions are made in the interests of the people, the provision of decent living conditions, on the other hand, when as a result of public decisions, deteriorating living conditions of people, then sanctions (moral, administrative, political, criminal, etc.) are applied to those who violate them. The responsibility of public authorities (ensuring the conditions for achieving the goal of public decision) and sanctions (inevitable punishment system, when the goal is not achieved, and living conditions deteriorated).

In this context, after acquiring international experience, one should turn to European and world experience. For example, only a wrongly word (in the context of its civil society assessment) automatically leads to the application of moral and administrative sanctions - such a person resigns.

Constitutional guarantees of public decisions should become the Basic Law of the state, which should contain a system of counterweight against the tyranny of state authorities (legislative, executive, judicial). For example, in the past years of the existence of the Ukrainian state, senior officials "tweaked" the Constitution "for themselves", which led to the usurpation of power. The protection of this should be the introduction of a new article of the Constitution of Ukraine that any version of the Fundamental Law leads to the dissolution of the Verkhovna Rada and the President, indicating that this composition of deputies in the future is not entitled to work in state authorities.

This will ensure the stability of the Constitution of the state and eliminate the attempts of various political forces to usurp power in society. The development and implementation of managerial decisions in public administration must be provided with a system of economic, political, environmental, information, social, etc. guarantees. Without a system of guarantees, as evidenced by the analysis of the experience of implementation of concepts, strategies, programs, since 1991 in Ukraine, they all remain on paper. No program of the Government, the concept of political parties on the reform of socio-economic development of Ukraine since 1991 has not been implemented, and the life of the people is constantly deteriorating, the number of citizens living below the poverty line is constantly increasing, there is an outflow of labor abroad, and state authorities (legislative, executive, judicial) are engaged in "struggle" against themselves (so-called struggle against corruption).

At the tenth stage, a system is developed for assessing the effectiveness of developing, adopting and implementing public management decisions, which completes the scientific and methodological support of this process. The effectiveness of public administration in general depends on the objective assessment of the decisions made. The assessment system includes criteria, indicators, time, place, grade, subjects and objects of evaluation, evaluation mechanism. In Ukraine, at the theoretical level, a methodology for evaluating the effectiveness of public management decisions [3] has been developed, but in the scientific articles, in the practice of management in the system of estimation there is a methodological chaos, there are no systematized methodological and methodological principles of evaluation, there is confusion between criteria and indicators of evaluation, there is no systemic, an objective view of the place, time, measure of evaluation. So, for example, between the criteria and indicators of evaluation put the sign of equality. Under the criteria understood indicators, but these are terms that reflect different processes,

stages of evaluation. Criteria are characterized by various factors of the process: economic, environmental, social, informational, etc.; the indicators specify each criterion. For example, the economic criterion may have many indicators: output of gross output, labor productivity, etc. The nature of the criteria, indicators depends on time, place and measure. For example, Ukrainian officials justify rising gas, light and water prices, arguing that prices in these countries are much higher in European countries. In this case, the economic situation in one country is automatically imposed on the economic situation in Ukraine, which leads to the absurdity of comparative assessment of prices for utilities, because it is necessary to take into account the place (country), time, and measure. In addition, evaluation systems need to take into account the closed, completed cycle in public administration, which should include the incomes of citizens in Ukraine, compare with them the possibility of paying citizens to raise prices for electricity, gas, etc. All this needs to be taken into account in the process of developing, adopting and implementing decisions in public administration.

The assessment of the effectiveness of the ratio "meta - results" characterizes the level of living conditions of citizens. For society, it is important that the results of public management meet the goal, which is a decent life for citizens. The standard of living of citizens is measured by the integrative index - the index of human development (HDI). In 2017, Ukraine was ranked 88th out of 189 countries for the HDI (Human Development Index, 2018).

Characteristics of the standard of living of citizens are carried out, for example, by determining the ratio of the cycle "justice - force". It should be noted that ensuring the rights and freedoms of man and their guarantees must determine the content and direction of the state. The state must respond to the person for their activities. The affirmation and maintenance of human rights and freedoms must in practice be the main responsibility of the state. "The right to determine and change the constitutional system in Ukraine belongs exclusively to the people and can not be usurped by the state, its organs or officials. No one can usurp state power" (Constitution of Ukraine, 1996). The lack of active force of the people to exercise their right to be the only source of power is confirmed by the current standard of living of citizens who have received an independent state, but almost 30 years do not yet have a decent standard of living. As a result, a situation emerged, about which in the seventeenth century. wrote the famous scholar Blaise Pascal: "Justice and power are disunited in this world, because the power does not want to listen to the voice of justice, does not want to know its evidence, nor arguments. The power itself is obvious and indisputable, it is more convincing than any arguments, and justice without power can be challenged. To justice rule the world, it must make it strong or force to be fair. But, failing to make a just strong, strong people declared fair. " Thus, this tyrannical force reigns - because force without justice is tyrannical "(Pascal, 2013).

An analysis of the practice of interaction between central government and local self-government has shown that the energy of the linear combination of components (actions of subjects, resources, legislative and normative support, etc.) of local self-government is used. Inclusion in the process of meeting the needs of citizens of the energy of network synergy requires the formation of closed, completed cycles of interaction between central government and local self-government.

Application of linear method of formation and realization of functions and tasks of local self-government, constant "naznirovanie" new laws, programs, tasks, etc. does

not complete the next stage of reform (according to the relevant criteria, for example, time), makes it permanent, transforms the process of reforming the relationship "center - region - community" into "stupid infinity." Confirmation of endless reformation is disharmony in the "meta-results" cycle, none of the declared programs of local self-government reform in Ukraine has achieved its goals.

The main function of a closed, completed cycle is to provide a causal relationship and the co-ordination of successive stages of the cycle, the transformation of local resources, actions of the subjects of relations, etc. in the potential of local self-government. The main result of the functioning of the local government network should be the new social value, new social values that should be: increased resources, new mechanisms, perfect tools, etc. Guaranteeing the rights and freedoms of the citizen and local communities.

Conclusions

Modern processes at the global level have led to the transformation of the state as an institution that faces the challenge of combining the pressure on the internal environment of global change with the need to ensure decent lives for citizens at the state and local levels. An analysis of practice certifies degradation of the social function of the state, which is the main factor of danger to the state system.

The transformation of the global environment, which is carried out at a rapid pace, makes it necessary to bring the state administration system, the relationship between public authorities and local governments into an adequate state, taking into account modern challenges at the state and local levels. One of the effective means is the use of preventive management method: problems are anticipated in advance, measures are being taken to prevent them. The essence of a completed, closed loop is revealed in the ratio of the purpose of government and its results. If the results meet the goal, the state administration has a completed, closed loop. Failure to achieve a socially important goal makes the cycle unfinished, which becomes a factor in the political, economic instability of the state. The publicly important goal of state administration should be to ensure a decent standard of living for the people.

The cycle has the appropriate sequence, the development of each phase, which is aimed at predicting problems, preparing tools for their elimination: preparation of definitions, definitions, categories; characteristic of object, object; carrying out an analysis of their functioning in practice; setting the goal of management; forecasting of desired and possible management results; establishment of subjects that will participate in the achievement of the goal, the definition of their powers, responsibility, the establishment of sanctions for non-fulfillment of authority; inventory of available resources that are needed to achieve the goal; definition of driving forces, contradictions, problems that are and which can be in the process of achieving the set goal, development of methods and mechanisms for their removal; development of strategy and tactics for achieving the goal; preparation of a mechanism for ensuring the achievement of the goal; development of a system for measuring and assessing the level of achievement of the set goal. Interaction and interdependence between the stages is universal: the change of parameters in one of the stages necessitates the alignment of all other stages. Changes can be made in real-time, providing an adequate response to internal and external challenges.

Promising areas for further research are improving tools for predicting possible problems and developing mechanisms for their elimination.

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